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IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN CHILDREN WITH ATOPIC DERMATITIS

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Abstract: The study was conducted to study the information content of the level of cytokines in assessing the functional changes in immunological parameters in children with atopic dermatitis. As the study showed, a comprehensive assessment of the level of cytokines makes it possible to assess the course of the inflammatory process, the effectiveness of the therapy and determine the strategy for further correction of treatment.

Keywords: children, atopic dermatitis, interleukins.

For all countries of the world, regardless of their level of economic development, a significant increase in the incidence of allergies in children is a serious problem. Among allergic dermatoses, atopic dermatitis (AD) occupies the first place. In Russia, the prevalence of AD in children, according to the unified international program ISAAC, ranges from 6.2% to 15.5%. [1, 2, 8].

Very often, AD is the debut manifestation of atopy - a hereditary predisposition to allergies, which in early childhood is expressed as a mucocutaneous syndrome with a predominant skin lesion, and subsequently can proceed as an atopic syndrome, in which skin manifestations are combined with bronchial asthma (BA), rhinosinusitis, etc.

A variety of cellular and humoral factors are involved in the implementation of the immune response to the allergen. A special role is assigned to the cytokine system. Cytokines are peptides, products of the synthesis of various cells, which ensure their interaction under normal conditions and when activated by allergens. In individuals with atopy, under the influence of genetic and environmental factors, predominantly the mechanisms controlled by the system of T-helpers of the Th2 type are activated, which leads to hyperproduction of specific Ig E by B-lymphocytes and the level of IL-4 is high. Other types of interleukins can also take part in the formation of various forms of the immune response, among which one of the leading places is occupied by IL-1, a polyfunctional cytokine synthesized by monocytes. In recent studies, a feature of the immune response in allergic diseases has been revealed:

Ambiguous results have been obtained on the content of IL-2 in the blood of children with atopy. So, some researchers point to elevated levels of IL-2 in the blood (Sentsova T. B., Revyakina V. A., Digilova N. D. 2002; Dontsova E. V. 2011), while others point to low values of this interleukin in patients with atopy (Sultanova N. G. 2008).

Given the leading role of immunological mechanisms in the pathogenesis of allergies, it is important to assess the state of changes in the immune system of patients with AD, in particular, the ability to produce cytokines and their dynamics.

Violation of the ratio of the latter is of great importance in the regulation of the immune response to the allergen, in the development and course of AD in children.

Purpose of the study: to evaluate the dynamics of immunological parameters in children with atopic dermatitis.

Materials and methods: To solve the problem, 72 children aged 4 to 12 years were examined. Of these, 39 children with atopic dermatitis (girls - 20, boys - 19) and 33 practically healthy children of the same age, gender, without signs of allergy. In all children with AD, we determined the integral indicator SCORAD by assessing objective (intensity and prevalence) and subjective (sleep disturbance and intensity of daytime pruritus) criteria. On the SCORAD scale, we evaluated six objective symptoms in points: erythema, edema/papular elements, crusts/weeping, excoriations, lichenification/desquamation, dry skin. We assessed the intensity of each symptom on a 4-level scale: 0-absent, 1-weak, 2-moderate, 3-strong. When estimating the affected area, we used «rule of nine». The calculation of the SCORAD index was made according to the formula: $SCORAD = A/5 + 7B/2 + C$, where A is the sum of the scores for the prevalence of skin lesions; B-sum of clinical symptom intensity scores; C is the sum of the scores of the intensity of subjective disorders according to the visual analogue scale [5].

To assess the cytokine profile in children in the main and comparison groups, the content of IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-4, IL-6 (pg / ml) was determined by enzyme immunoassay using test systems of CJSC Vector-Best (Novosibirsk region, Russia), and in children with AD, cytokines were studied during the period of exacerbation and after 1 month.

Results and its discussion: As the study showed, 7 children with AD (17.9%) had a mild course, 27 had a moderate course (69.3%), and 5 had a severe course (12.8%) of the disease according to SCORAD. There were no significant differences in severity between boys and girls, which allowed us to assess the level of IL in the blood serum of children with AD without gender (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of the level of interleukins in blood serum in patients with atopic dermatitis (pg/ml)

	IL-2	IL-4	IL-1 β	IL-6
Patients with AD at admission (N-39)	3.33 $\pm$ 0.32	1.32 $\pm$ 0.19*	0.69 $\pm$ 0.06*	1.27 $\pm$ 0.14*
Patients with AD at discharge (N-39)	3.90 $\pm$ 0.42	1.15 $\pm$ 0.26	0.57 $\pm$ 0.04**	1.26 $\pm$ 0.25
Comparison group (N-33)	3.34 $\pm$ 0.71	0.46 $\pm$ 0.25	0.27 $\pm$ 0.05	0.76 $\pm$ 0.12

Note: * $p < 0.02 - 0.001$ - significant between groups of children with AD and control during exacerbation; ** $p < 0.001$ - significant between groups of children with AD after treatment and control.

In children with AD, there were no significant differences in the level of IL-2 at admission compared with the control group, but there was an increase in the production of IL-4 during exacerbation, which indicates the activation of Th2 cells. In individuals with atopy, the content of the Th2 subpopulation of T-lymphocytes-helpers that produce IL-4 (B-cell Stimulatory Factor1), IL-6 is increased. For the early phase of allergic inflammation, which develops 15-60 minutes after repeated exposure to the allergen, mast cells release histamine, proteases, form and secrete leukotrienes, prostaglandins, cytokines (particularly IL-1) and chemotaxis factors, which contribute to the expansion and damage blood vessels, the influx of blood cells, and clinically this is manifested by itching and swelling [6]. In this way, constant mechanical stimulation (scratching) is one of the reasons for the release of large amounts of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β , by epidermal cells. As our study showed, an increase in IL-6, IL-1 β serves as confirmation of the participation in the pathogenesis of dendritic, mast cells and keratinocytes. A month after the course of treatment, significant differences remain between the groups of children with AD and control only in terms of the level of IL-1s ($p < 0.001$). The level of IL-4 in patients with AD after a month did not significantly differ from the control group, but remained 2.5 times higher than in children without allergies. A month after the course of treatment, significant differences remain between the groups of children with AD and control only in terms of the level of IL-1s ($p < 0.001$). The level of IL-4 in patients with AD after a month did not significantly differ from the control group, but remained 2.5 times higher than in children without allergies. A month after the course of treatment, significant differences remain between the groups of children with AD and control only in terms of the level of IL-1s ($p < 0.001$). The level of IL-4 in patients with AD after a month did not significantly differ from the control group, but remained 2.5 times higher than in children without allergies.

Upon admission to the hospital, the average score on the SCORAD scale was 31.53 ± 1.88 , which corresponds to the moderate severity of AD. In the course of treatment, positive dynamics was clinically noted, reflected in a decrease in itching, the absence of new elements, a decrease in the area of damage and normalization of sleep, which was also reflected in the assessment on the SCORAD scale.

During the re-examination of patients, a month after the start of treatment, the average values on the SCORAD scale were 19.05 ± 1.54 points. Thus, a month after the start of treatment, changes in the parameters of immunological reactivity persist in the blood, and patients with AD need further continuation of therapy. As the exacerbation of blood pressure subsides, a gradual decrease in IL-4 and an increase in IL-2 are observed, which may indicate the dominance of the Th-1 response in patients with a chronic form of allergy.

Conclusions: 1. Evaluation of immunological parameters allows us to evaluate the course of the inflammatory process, the effectiveness of the therapy and

determine the strategy for further correction of treatment to achieve the maximum (favorable) effect.

2. An imbalance between Th-1 and Th-2 plays an important role in the immune response in atopic dermatitis, towards an increase in the differentiation of the latter. The level of IL-2 in patients with exacerbation of atopic dermatitis does not significantly differ from the control group, which also confirms the dominant role of Th2-lymphocytes in allergic inflammation.

3. Despite the clinical improvement on the background of traditional therapy, signs of immune inflammation persist in the blood serum, which requires a longer anti-inflammatory therapy, as well as the search for new methods of treatment that can improve the patient's quality of life.

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